

Enhancing Learning Outcomes Through Activity-Based Module Delivery: A Study on the “Philosophical Thoughts on Primary Education” Module in the BEd (Hons) Primary Education Programme

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Introduction: The quality of teacher training is important for the success of primary education. The B.Ed (Hons) Primary Education program was started in Sri Lanka because there isn't much specialized training for primary school teachers. However, the first group did poorly in the "Philosophical Thoughts on Primary Education" module because the lectures were uninteresting. This study looks into whether learning through activities leads to better results.

Objectives: (1) to compare performance between lecture-based and activity-based delivery; (2) to find out what restricts students from being engaged; (3) to use activity-based lesson plans; (4) to investigate how the intervention worked; and (5) to explore how students' views on educational philosophy changed.

Methodology: A qualitative-dominant, comparative case study looked at two groups: Cohort 1 (40 people who learned through lectures online) and Cohort 2 (40 people who learned through activities in person). Grades, reflective journals, observations by teachers, and focus group discussions were all part of the data. Both thematic and descriptive analyses were used. The methodology aligns well with the objectives: grades enabled comparison of performance, while reflective journals and focus group discussions uncovered restrictions to engagement and traced changes in students' philosophical views. Activity-based lesson plans implemented in Cohort 2 were examined, and how the intervention works was investigated through content and thematic analysis.

Results & Discussion: Cohort 2 did much better: In Cohort 1, 25% scored more than 65. Activities like debates and role-plays helped students apply what they learned in real life, even though they didn't like the abstract content at first. The results are in line with constructivist theory, which shows that activity-based learning works in teacher education.

Conclusion: Activity-based delivery makes people much more interested and productive. Suggestions include schools using interactive teaching methods and doing long-term studies on student retention. This study helps to reach SDG 4 by showing how to train teachers in ways that work.

Keywords: Activity-based learning, Constructivism, Educational philosophy, Primary education
Teacher training